

Ag⁺ Catalysed Oxidation of Some Typical Functional Groups by Ceric Salts in H₂SO₄ and HNO₃ Media

Y. RAJESWAR RAO and P. K. SAIPRAKASH*

Department of Chemistry, Nizam College, Hyderabad-500 001

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A comparative study of the Ag⁺ catalysed oxidation of ethanol, formaldehyde, acetone and acetic acid by ceric nitrate in HNO₃ medium and ceric sulphate in H₂SO₄ medium was undertaken to explain the mechanism of the catalysed reaction. The change in Ce⁴⁺ reactive species in the two different media produces a marked effect in the relative rates of the catalysed and uncatalysed reaction. The catalysis was found to be more pronounced in the H₂SO₄ medium. The order of [Ce⁴⁺] was found to be one and that of [Ag⁺] was fractional in both the media studied. When low concentration of [Ag⁺] was employed the order was nearly one in sulphuric acid medium. The order of the [substrate] changed from unity in the uncatalysed reaction to fractional order in the catalysed reaction in H₂SO₄ medium. However, in HNO₃ medium the order of the [substrate] was found to be fractional both in the catalysed and uncatalysed reactions. A mechanism involving the formation of (Ag-substrate)⁺ adduct and the reaction of Ce⁴⁺ species or (Ce⁴⁺-substrate) complex with the Ag⁺-adduct was proposed to explain the kinetic data.

CERIC salts in various acid media are well known to oxidise carbon compounds via formation of 1:1 Ce⁴⁺-substrate complex¹ which unimolecularly dissociates in the rate determining step. In the oxidation of alcohols by Ce⁴⁺ in nitric acid medium it was shown^{2,3} that neutral ceric nitrate molecule Ce(NO₃)₄ was the active species. However, in the oxidations by Ce⁴⁺ in sulphuric acid medium the evidence both for the formation of Ce⁴⁺-substrate complex and the nature of the active species reported by earlier workers was conflicting⁴⁻⁷. Our earlier work⁸ on the oxidation of ethyl and benzyl alcohols by Ce⁴⁺ in sulphuric and acetic acid mixtures indicated no complex formation between Ce⁴⁺ and the alcohol and it was concluded that neutral Ce(SO₄)₂ might be the active species. Ag⁺ ion catalysis in Ce⁴⁺ oxidations was observed by Sinha⁹ in the oxidation of TI⁺ in HNO₃ medium and it was reported that the order of [Ce⁴⁺], [TI⁺], [Ag⁺] was one each. From the kinetic data it was concluded that catalysis occurs via the formation of 1:1 TI⁺-Ce⁴⁺ complex. Since Ag⁺ is known to form adducts with oxygen containing compounds¹⁰⁻¹², with lone pair of electrons on the oxygen atom, it was thought worthwhile to study the effect of Ag⁺ ion on the oxidation of some typical functional groups containing oxygen by Ce⁴⁺ both in sulphuric and nitric acid media.

Experimental

Ceric nitrate or ceric sulphate solutions were prepared by dissolving ceric ammonium nitrate (Baker analysed reagent) or ceric ammonium sulphate (E. Merck) in nitric or sulphuric acid solutions of known strength. The substrates used were purified by standard methods and silver nitrate was BDH (AnalaR) grade.

The rate of the reaction was followed by estimating the unreacted Ce⁴⁺ at different time intervals by quenching aliquots of the reaction mixture in known excess ferrous ammonium sulphate and titrating the unreacted ferrous against standard ceric sulphate using ferroin indicator.

The oxidation of ethanol, formaldehyde and acetone yield acetaldehyde¹, formic acid⁵ and mixture of formic and acetic acids⁷. The oxidative decarboxylation of acetic acid yields CO₂ along with methanol and methyl acetate¹³. Suitable spot tests¹⁴ were carried out to confirm the products. The stoichiometry of the reactions were found to be same in the presence and absence of Ag⁺, viz.,

Results and Discussion

Ce⁴⁺-Substrate reactions in H₂SO₄ medium :

Under the conditions [substrate] ≫ [Ce⁴⁺] the order of [Ce⁴⁺] was found to be unity, both in the presence and absence of Ag⁺, as indicated by straight lines obtained by plotting log a/a-x vs time (Fig. 1A,B). From the slopes of these plots the observed pseudo first order rate constants (k') were evaluated. The concentration of Ag⁺ was found to be unchanged at the end of the reaction as indicated by the constant thiocyanate titre values. Increase in concentration of the substrate increased the rate and the order of [substrate] was found to be one in the absence of Ag⁺ but was fractional in

- (A) Plot of log a/a-x vs time in the Ce⁴⁺-ethanol reaction (uncatalysed).
[Ce⁴⁺]=0.006 mol. dm⁻³; [ethanol]=1.0 mol. dm⁻³; [H₂SO₄]=1.0 mol. dm⁻³, temp.=50°C.
- (B) Plot of log a/a-x vs time Ag⁺ catalysed reaction [Ag⁺]=0.01 mol. dm⁻³; other conditions same as in (A).
- (C) Plot of log k' + 3 vs log [ethanol] + 1 in the presence of Ag⁺ [Ag⁺]=0.01 mol. dm⁻³; other conditions same as in (A).
- (D) Plot of log k' + 3 vs log [Ag⁺] + 3. [ethanol]=1.0 mol. dm⁻³; other conditions same as in (A).
- (E) Plot of 1/k' × 10³ vs 1/[ethanol]. Conditions same as in (C).

the presence of Ag⁺ (Fig. 1C) (Table 1). The k' values increased with increase in [Ag⁺] (Table 2) (Fig. 1D) and the order of [Ag⁺] was found to be nearly one in the low concentration region, however it was fractional when higher concentrations of Ag⁺ were employed. The formation of free radicals was indicated by the induced polymerisation of acrylamide⁹. The fractional order of [substrate] in the presence of Ag⁺ indicates that the substrate is involved in a complex formation with Ag⁺ or Ce⁴⁺. Our earlier work⁸ shows that the substrate in sulphuric acid medium does not form kinetically detectable complexes with Ce⁴⁺. Ag⁺ is known to form adducts with oxygen containing compounds with lone pair of electrons on oxygen atom¹⁰⁻¹². Hence, we assume the formation of an adduct between Ag⁺ and the substrate as the first step which later reacts with Ce⁴⁺ to give (Ag-S)²⁺, the formation of Ag²⁺ intermediate was verified by the bipyridyl test¹³. Hence the general mechanism could be written as follows :

Since [Ag⁺] ≪ [S] the rate equation from above mechanism could be written as

$$\frac{-d[Ce^{4+}]}{dt} = \frac{k_1 K_1 [Ce^{4+}][S][Ag^+]}{1 + K_1 [S]} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{-2.303 \frac{d \log [Ce^{4+}]}{dt}}{dt} = k' = \frac{k_1 K_1 [S][Ag^+]}{1 + K_1 [S]} \quad (2)$$

TABLE 1

EFFECT OF [SUBSTRATE] ON k' IN THE Ag⁺-CATALYSED Ce⁴⁺-SUBSTRATE REACTIONS IN H₂SO₄ IN MEDIUM

(A) [Ce ⁴⁺]=0.006 mol. dm ⁻³ ; [Ag ⁺]=0.01 mol. dm ⁻³ ;	[H ₂ SO ₄]=1.0 mol. dm ⁻³ ; temp.=40°C				
[HCHO] mol. dm ⁻³	0.50	0.75	1.00	2.00	3.00
k' × 10 ³ min ⁻¹	7.64	8.20	9.66	14.26	17.25
(B) [Ce ⁴⁺]=0.0047 mol. dm ⁻³ ; [Ag ⁺]=0.01 mol. dm ⁻³ ;	[H ₂ SO ₄]=1.0 mol. dm ⁻³ ; temp.=45°C				
[CH ₃ COCH ₃] mol. dm ⁻³	0.20	0.25	0.40	0.50	0.60
k' × 10 ³ min ⁻¹	1.75	2.14	3.06	3.59	4.60
(C) [Ce ⁴⁺]=0.0074 mol. dm ⁻³ ; [Ag ⁺]=0.02 mol. dm ⁻³ ;	[H ₂ SO ₄]=0.97 mol. dm ⁻³ ; temp.=65°C				
[CH ₃ COOH] mol. dm ⁻³	0.2	0.4	0.6	0.8	1.0
k' × 10 ³ min ⁻¹	1.54	2.57	3.33	4.14	4.69
					1.2
					5.06
					1.6
					5.70

* Ce(SO₄)₂ is written for simplicity as Ce⁴⁺.

TABLE 2
EFFECT OF [Ag⁺] ON k' IN Ce⁴⁺-SUBSTRATE REACTIONS IN H₂SO₄ MEDIUM

(A) [Ce ⁴⁺]=0.006 mol. dm ⁻³ ; [H ₂ SO ₄]=1.0 mol. dm ⁻³ ;	[HCHO]=1.0 mol. dm ⁻³ ; temp.=50°C						
[Ag ⁺] × 10 ³ mol. dm ⁻³	8.0	10.0	14.0	16.0	18.0	21.0	25.0
k' × 10 ³ min ⁻¹	2.71	2.99	3.22	3.60	3.78	4.06	4.41
(B) [Ce ⁴⁺]=0.0047 mol. dm ⁻³ ; [CH ₃ OCH ₃]=1.0 mol. dm ⁻³ ;	[H ₂ SO ₄]=1.0 mol. dm ⁻³ ; temp.=35°C						
[Ag ⁺] × 10 ³ mol. dm ⁻³	1.4	1.8	2.2	3.0	3.5	4.0	4.0
k' × 10 ³ min ⁻¹	3.59	4.00	4.28	4.74	5.26	5.51	5.51
(C) [Ce ⁴⁺]=0.0051 mol. dm ⁻³ ; [H ₂ SO ₄]=1.0 mol. dm ⁻³ ;	[CH ₃ COOH]=3.20 mol. dm ⁻³ ; temp.=50°C						
[Ag ⁺] × 10 ³ mol. dm ⁻³	1.0	2.0	3.0	4.0	5.0	6.0	6.0
k' × 10 ³ min ⁻¹	1.47	2.62	3.04	4.05	5.06	6.21	6.21

This accounts for the first order dependence on [Ce⁴⁺], and fractional order with respect to [substrate] and [Ag⁺]. However, when very low concentration of the catalyst was employed the order of [Ag⁺] becomes nearly one. Taking the reciprocals of equation (2)

$$\frac{1}{k'} = \frac{1}{k_1 K_1 [S] [Ag^+]} + \frac{1}{k_1 [Ag^+]} \quad (3)$$

and plotting 1/k' vs 1/[S] at constant [Ag⁺] a straight line graph with an intercept was obtained (Fig. 1E). From the slope and intercept values the formation constant (K₁) and the rate constant (k₁) were evaluated in all the cases (Table 3). The effect of ionic strength (μ) was studied in the catalysed reaction with varying [ammonium sulphate] and it was found to have a decreasing effect on the k' values (Table 6). This could be probably due to the formation of higher sulphato species such as Ce(SO₄)₂²⁻ or HCe(SO₄)₂ thus reducing the concentration of the reactive Ce(SO₄)₂ species.

TABLE 3

FORMATION CONSTANTS (K₁) AND RATE CONSTANTS k₁ IN THE Ce⁴⁺-SUBSTRATE REACTIONS CATALYSED BY Ag⁺ IN H₂SO₄ MEDIUM

Substrate	k ₁ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	K ₁ dm ³ mol ⁻¹	temp. °C
Ethanol	2.25	0.81	50
Formaldehyde	0.38	4.12	40
Acetone	0.50	1.89	45
Acetic acid	2.0	0.25	65

TABLE 4

EFFECT OF [SUBSTRATE] ON THE k_{obs} IN THE Ce⁴⁺-SUBSTRATE REACTIONS IN HNO₃ MEDIUM CATALYSED BY Ag⁺

(A) [Ce ⁴⁺]=0.006 mol. dm ⁻³ ; [Ag ⁺]=0.01 mol. dm ⁻³ ;	[HNO ₃]=1.0 mol. dm ⁻³ ; temp.=31°C						
[C ₂ H ₅ OH] mol. dm ⁻³	0.05	0.10	0.15	0.20	0.25	0.30	0.40
k _{obs} × 10 ³ min ⁻¹	5.64	8.35	10.88	12.95	14.15	15.36	16.56
(B) [Ce ⁴⁺]=0.001 mol. dm ⁻³ ; [Ag ⁺]=0.02 mol. dm ⁻³ ;	[HNO ₃]=1.0 mol. dm ⁻³ ; temp.=15°C						
[HCHO] mol. dm ⁻³	0.01	0.02	0.04	0.05	0.06	0.06	0.06
k _{obs} × 10 ³ min ⁻¹	3.22	5.29	10.12	13.34	16.33	16.33	16.33
(C) [Ce ⁴⁺]=0.0056 mol. dm ⁻³ ; [Ag ⁺]=0.02 mol. dm ⁻³ ;	[HNO ₃]=1.0 mol. dm ⁻³ ; temp.=23°C						
[CH ₃ COCH ₃] mol. dm ⁻³	0.05	0.10	0.15	0.20	0.30	0.40	0.48
k _{obs} × 10 ³ min ⁻¹	9.66	14.26	17.90	22.54	31.74	36.03	42.55
(D) [Ce ⁴⁺]=0.0026 mol. dm ⁻³ ; [Ag ⁺]=0.01 mol. dm ⁻³ ;	[HNO ₃]=1.0 mol. dm ⁻³ ; temp.=30.4°C						
[HOAc] mol. dm ⁻³	0.23	0.35	0.46	0.92	1.15	1.38	1.38
k _{obs} × 10 ³ min ⁻¹	5.40	5.41	7.19	8.16	9.09	9.89	9.89

TABLE 5

EFFECT OF [Ag⁺] ON THE k_{obs} IN THE Ce⁴⁺-SUBSTRATE REACTIONS IN HNO₃ MEDIUM

(A) [Ce ⁴⁺]=0.006 mol. dm ⁻³ ; [C ₂ H ₅ OH]=0.1 mol. dm ⁻³ ;	[HNO ₃]=1.0 mol. dm ⁻³ ; temp.=31°C						
[Ag ⁺] mol. dm ⁻³	0.03	0.04	0.05	0.06	0.08	0.10	0.15
k _{obs} × 10 ³ min ⁻¹	9.05	10.58	11.50	12.80	13.57	15.48	18.86
(B) [Ce ⁴⁺]=0.001 mol. dm ⁻³ ; [HCHO]=0.02 mol. dm ⁻³ ;	[HNO ₃]=1.0 mol. dm ⁻³ ; temp.=15°C						
[Ag ⁺] mol. dm ⁻³	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.04	0.06	0.06	0.06
k _{obs} × 10 ³ min ⁻¹	2.99	5.29	8.05	10.12	13.11	13.11	13.11
(C) [Ce ⁴⁺]=0.0056 mol. dm ⁻³ ; [CH ₃ COCH ₃]=0.10 mol. dm ⁻³ ;	[HNO ₃]=1.0 mol. dm ⁻³ ; temp.=23°C						
[Ag ⁺] mol. dm ⁻³	0.01	0.015	0.02	0.03	0.04	0.05	0.06
k _{obs} × 10 ³ min ⁻¹	9.66	10.81	13.60	16.62	18.86	22.54	24.84
(D) [Ce ⁴⁺]=0.00264 mol. dm ⁻³ ; [HOAc]=0.46 mol. dm ⁻³ ;	[HNO ₃]=1.0 mol. dm ⁻³ ; temp.=30.4°C						
[Ag ⁺] mol. dm ⁻³	0.003	0.004	0.006	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.04
k _{obs} × 10 ³ min ⁻¹	3.97	4.54	6.70	7.19	14.70	20.20	27.40

The reactions were carried out at four different temperatures and the overall activation parameters are presented in Table 8.

Ce⁴⁺-substrate reactions in HNO₃ medium :

The uncatalysed reaction between Ce⁴⁺ and these substrates in nitric acid medium could be explained by a general mechanism involving the formation of 1:1 Ce⁴⁺-substrate complex as follows :

The above mechanism gives a rate law,

$$\frac{-d[Ce^{4+}]}{dt} = \frac{k_2 K_2 [Ce^{4+}] [S]}{1 + K_2 [S]} \quad (4)$$

TABLE 6

EFFECT OF IONIC STRENGTH ON THE k' IN THE Ce⁴⁺-SUBSTRATE REACTIONS CATALYSED BY Ag⁺

[Ce⁴⁺]=8.0 × 10⁻³ mol. dm⁻³ ; [H₂SO₄]=0.8 mol. dm⁻³ ;
[Ag⁺]=0.01 mol. dm⁻³ ; temp. (a) 40°; (b) 40°; (c) 40°;
(d) 60°C

[substrate] mol. dm⁻³ ; (a) C₂H₅OH=0.2; (b) HCHO=0.5;
(c) CH₃COCH₃=0.20;
(d) CH₃COOH=3.31.

	μ mol. dm ⁻³	0.94	1.14	2.14	2.64	3.34
(a) k' × 10 ³	2.60	2.44	2.01	1.50	1.32	1.32
(b) k' × 10 ³	8.40	7.10	6.67	6.20	3.80	3.80
(c) k' × 10 ³	6.90	5.30	4.40	2.18	1.50	1.50
(d) k' × 10 ³	3.00	2.00	1.30	1.00	0.72	0.72

TABLE 7

EFFECT OF IONIC STRENGTH ON THE "k_{obs} IN THE Ce⁴⁺-SUBSTRATE REACTIONS CATALYSED BY Ag⁺

[Ce⁴⁺]=5.08 × 10⁻³ mol. dm⁻³ ;
[Ag⁺]=0.01 mol. dm⁻³ ;
[substrate] mol. dm⁻³ ;

[HNO₃]=1.0 mol. dm⁻³ ;
temp. (a) 30°C; (b) 15°C; (c) 30°C; (d) 40°C
(a) C₂H₅OH=0.2; (b) HCHO=0.025;
(c) CH₃COCH₃=0.20; (d) CH₃COOH=0.66

μ mol. dm ⁻³	1.07	1.27	1.47	1.67	1.87	2.07
(a) k _{obs} × 10 ³ min ⁻¹	5.10	4.90	4.60	4.20	4.20	4.20
(b) k _{obs} × 10 ³ min ⁻¹	10.40	9.00	9.00	9.00	9.00	9.00
(c) k _{obs} × 10 ³ min ⁻¹	3.30	2.50	2.50	2.50	2.50	2.50
(d) k _{obs} × 10 ³ min ⁻¹	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.10	1.12

* Ce(NO₃)₄ is written for simplicity as Ce⁴⁺ in HNO₃ medium.

TABLE 8

ACTIVATION PARAMETERS Ce⁴⁺-SUBSTRATE REACTIONS CATALYSED BY Ag⁺

(a) Ceric sulphate-substrate reaction.

(b) Ceric nitrate-substrate reaction.

Parameter	Ethylalcohol	Formaldehyde	Acetone	Acetic acid
E _a k J mole ⁻¹	(a) 91.83 (b) 40.77	86.11 120.88	57.34 60.04	95.72 63.66
ΔH [‡] k J mole ⁻¹	(a) 89.16 (b) 38.34	83.43 118.50	54.72 62.63	92.92 61.14
ΔG [‡] k J mole ⁻¹	(a) 100.86 (b) 80.56	100.11 85.65	96.14 82.20	110.39 80.92
ΔS [‡] J K ⁻¹ mole ⁻¹	(a) - 36.24 (b) - 144.04	- 51.62 114.50	- 130.29 - 67.24	- 51.71 - 65.17

which explains the first order dependence of [Ce⁴⁺] and the fractional order of [S]. In the Ag⁺ catalysed reaction also the order of [Ce⁴⁺] was one and that of [S] and [Ag⁺] fractional as can be computed from the values given in Tables 4 and 5. As catalysis was observed both in sulphuric and nitric acid media it is reasonable to assume that the first step is the formation of (Ag-S)⁺ adduct. Kinetic and optical evidence indicates that a complex is also formed during the catalysed reaction. Hence the probable mechanism could be written as follows :

The rate equation considering the above scheme

comes out to be

$$\begin{aligned} -2.303 \frac{d \log [\text{Ce}^{4+}]}{dt} &= k_{obs} \\ &= \frac{k_3 K_3 K_4 [\text{Ag}^+] [\text{S}]}{1/[\text{S}]\{1 + K_4 [\text{Ag}^+]\} + K_3 + K_4 + K_3 K_4 [\text{Ag}^+] + K_3 K_4 [\text{S}]} \quad (5) \end{aligned}$$

The above equation accounts for the first order dependence on [Ce⁴⁺] and fractional order of [Ag⁺] and [S]. Owing to the complexity of the equation (5), the individual constants K₃, K₄ and k₃ could not be determined as was done in sulphuric acid medium. The effect of μ on k_{obs} values in the ceric nitrate-substrate reactions was not marked (Table 7). As in the uncatalysed reactions^{2,3} the reactive Ce⁴⁺ species in nitric acid medium is considered to be Ce(NO₃)₄ neutral molecule in the concentration range studied (1.0-1.5 mol.dm⁻³HNO₃). The overall activation parameters are presented in Table 8.

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